

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme on Oral Hygiene Status among Selected School Children of Age Group between 6-14 Years in Selected School of Greater Noida, UP.

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Abstract:-

Background: Nursing is a one of the oldest and noblest Professionalism. It needs love and deserves tender attention. It is one of the most entertaining arts that requires a combination of knowledge, skills and values. **Aim:** To evaluate the effectiveness of the oral hygiene education program in students of age group between 6-14 years in selected school of greater noida. **Methodology:** The study has adopted a cross sectional descriptive design with convenience sampling technique. Data was collected from Delhi world school and Analyze and interpret data by descriptive and inferential statistics. The tool is socio demographic and likert scale on attitude toward girl abuse. **Result:** The frequency and percentage distribution of study participants was described. The overall mean and S.D senior secondary student toward girl abuse was \pm SD of 74.20 ± 13.67 . The association between attitude and selected socio demographic variable was significantly related to class, gender, monthly income, father and mother education with ($p < 0.05$). The study concluded most of the participants were aware about girl abuse.

Keyword:- Girl Abuse, Senior Secondary students, Attitude.

I. INTRODUCTION

Childhood is the period to learn the values and competencies that bring the child to adult world. Childhood is the peak time to initiate teaching good habits, morality and discipline. Likewise, childhood is important and appropriate time to teach hygienic practices. The word hygiene is derived from the name of the ancient Greek goddess of healthful living Hygein. Hygiene refers to the set of practices associated with the preservation of health and healthy living. Cleanliness helps us to live healthy and sound. Personal hygiene is important to keep ourselves clean and tidy. It includes hygiene of the skin, mouth, hand, hair, nails, feet etc.

For growing children, oral hygiene is a very important factor. Oral hygiene not only makes them comfortable, but it teaches them to do what is right and what is wrong. Early hygiene enhancement gives the child a healthy and comfortable life, and will teach them to be hygienic up to the time they grow old. Children are high risk of infection due to their enthusiasm to touch, reach and grasp to learn about environment. To teach children hygiene, start from setting

examples and make them follow it. Oral hygiene is important at every stage of life, but good habits start in childhood. Children who learn hygiene and how to practice hygiene should carry it into adulthood. Hygiene education starts at home and ends with children learning to clean themselves and follow hygiene rules, having a new child may be more difficult in the transition to adulthood. Learning proper cleanliness skills can help the children to prevent the spread of germs and illness.

Poor sanitation and high population density act as a double whammy on Indian children half of whom grow up stunted". States with the worst health conditions and largest populations like Bihar, Jharkhand, and Madhya Pradesh are said to have the most malnourished children in the country, with more than about 48% of children are suffering from some degree of oral disease in India due to poor oral hygiene. Studies have showed that 638 million people defecating in the open, and 44% of mothers do so in the open Child's feces, which is mouth indicates a high risk of disease.

Oral hygiene is the practice of keeping the mouth clean by brushing the teeth and cleaning the tongue. Social approval is gained through these personal qualities. However, good or effective oral hygiene is rarely recognized and considered a preventive measure. Oral hygiene involves practice of keeping oneself clean in order to prevent illness and diseases. Keeping oneself clean will not only protect one from germs but also allows having confidence in relationships and social life. Actions to ensure oral hygiene are simple but most of people neglect to practice the habit.

II. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

"A study to assess the effectiveness of planned teaching programme on oral hygiene status among selected school children of age group between 6-14 years in selected school of Uttar Pradesh".

III. OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- To evaluate knowledge regarding oral hygiene among primary school children
- To evaluate level of practice regarding oral hygiene among primary school children
- To assess effectiveness of planned teaching program on oral hygiene on knowledge and practice level regarding oral hygiene among primary school children
- To rule out association between knowledge and practice level regarding oral hygiene.

IV. HYPOTHESIS

HO: There will be no significant relationship between knowledge and practice score levels on oral hygiene of primary school children with selected demographic variables.

V. ASSUMPTION

- The primary school children may have some knowledge on oral hygiene.
- Video-assisted teaching programme may enhance knowledge and practice of primary school children on oral hygiene.

VI. RESEARCH APPROACH

Quantitative Research approach was used in this study.

VII. RESEARCH DESIGN

Design used in the study was Cross Sectional Descriptive design.

VIII. RESEARCH SETTING

The study was conducted in the month of October 2022 at senior secondary school, student of Greater Noida recognized by U.P. state government. Data collected from Sanskar Bharti Public School.

IX. POPULATION

Study population was Senior Secondary School students of Greater Noida.

X. SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The investigator selected the participants which were convenient, easily accessible. The convenient sampling used by investigator to get the participants. A total of 30 participants were selected to assess the knowledge regarding oral hygiene status among school going children.

A. SAMPLE SIZE

30 participants expected from Sanskar Bharti Public school, Greater Noida U.P.

B. SAMPLING ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

➤ Inclusion criteria

- *Senior secondary school students only.
- Senior secondary school students are present at that time of study.

➤ Exclusion criteria

- *Senior secondary school students are not willing to participate.
- Senior secondary school students are not present at the time of data collection

Majority of participants are 6 – 8 years old, that is, 49 (81.6%), followed by the participants in the age group of 9 – 11, i.e., 11(18.3%).

Fig. 1: A pie graph showing percentage distribution of participants in different age groups.

Majority of participants belong to Urban area, i.e, 43(71.6%), followed by the participants living in rural area, i.e, 17(28.3%).

Fig. 2: A pie graph showing percentage distribution of urban and rural.

Majority of participants have nuclear family i.e, 46(76.6%), 13(21.6%) participants have joint family and only one 1(1.6%) participant have extended family.

Fig. 3: A pie graph showing percentage distribution of type of families.

Majority of participants are Hindu, i.e, 46(76.6%), followed by participants who are Christian i.e, 9(15%),

5(8.3%) participants are Muslim. None of the participants are in the Sikh religion.

Fig. 4: A bar graph showing percentage distribution of religions.

Table 5: Distribution Of Respondents By Family Monthly Income

MONTHLY INCOME IN (Rs)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
>20,000	1	1.6
20,000 – 30,000	9	15
30,000 -40,000	14	23.3
Above 40,000	36	60
TOTAL	60	100

n = 60

Majority of participants have monthly income above 40,000 i.e, 36(60%) followed by the participants with monthly income 30,000 – 40,000 is 14(23.3%), 9(15%)20,000 30,000,1(1.6%) >20,000.

Majority of participants have previous knowledge regarding diabetic foot ulcer 40(66.6%), 20(33.3%) have no previous knowledge regarding oral hygiene.

Fig. 6: A bar graph showing percentage distribution of previous knowledge regarding oral hygiene

Majority of participants use Nursing Books for gathering information i.e, 33(55%), 27(45%) participants have acquired knowledge regarding diabetic foot ulcer from

Internet and social websites. None of the participants are in Radio and Television and Newspaper and magazines.

Fig. 7: A bar graph showing percentage distribution of source of information.

Source of information

• **SECTION II:** Finding related to knowledge of nursing students regarding oral hygiene

Table 8: Mean, Median and Standard deviation of knowledge score.

N= 60

TOTAL SCORE	MEAN	MEDIAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
513	8.5	9	3.461

XI. DISCUSSION

The current study focuses on knowledge about oral hygiene among school going children of selected school situated in Greater Noida,U.P. A descriptive design was adopted to assess the attitude of senior secondary students towards girl abuse.. Data was collected from 101 participants from Sanskar Bharti Public school, greater Noida, and U.P. using convenient sampling technique. Throughout the study, it was taken care to minimize bias and enhance the validity of study findings.In the present study class of the participants were know about oral hygiene. Result shows senior secondary students are positively motivated about girl abuse to prohibit this. In the present study states children of the participants were aware about oral hygiene.

XII. SUMMARY

Assessment of oral hygiene knowledge of students in s elected schools in Greater Noida Oral hygiene knowledge of students in selected schools in Noida. The aim is to measure students' oral hygiene knowledge regarding oral hygiene among school children of selected Schools of Greater Noida, U.P. The objective was to assess the knowledge regarding oral hygiene among school going children . Pilot study was

carried out from 25-05-2021 to 26-05-2021. Study was found feasible. Data collection of the study was carried out from 20-06-2021 to 30-06-2021. Analysis of data was done in accordance with the objectives by using descriptive statistics such as mean, percentage, range, standard deviation and inferential statistics such as chi-square, Fisher's exact test, Yate's correction test.The result of the study reveals that maximum of subjects according totheir age shows that 3(3%) were in age group of 15-16 years, 37(36.6%) were in the age group of 17- 18 years, 35 (35.5%) of subjects were in the age group of 19-20 years and 26(25.75) were in the age group of above 20 years. Majority 55(54.5%) of the subjects were female and only 46(45.5%) were male. most of the subjects 72(71.3%) were Hindu, 13(12.9%) were other, 10 (9.9%) were Christian and only 6(5.9 %) were Muslim. Majority of the subjects 55(54.5%) were from science background and 29(28.7%) were other subject whereas 17(16.8%) were arts..Shows the distribution of subject according to education of father, that the data revealed that 39(38.6%) were having secondary education while 21(20.8%) were having primary education 34(33.7%) were graduated and above and 7(7.0%) were no formal education.Shows the distribution of subject according to education of mother. The data revealed that 30(29.7%) were having primary education followed by

31(30.7%) were having secondary education while 25(24.8%) were graduated and above and 15(14.9%) were no formal education. Most of them are from the metropolitan area that is 32(35.7%), rural area is 36(31.7%) whereas urban area are 33(32.7%). The school management are mostly government 37(36.6) whereas private are 58(57.85) and others are 6(5.9%). The mostly source of information is from the family 30(29.7), social media 30(29.7) and friends 28(27.7 %) and T.V. is 13(12.9%).

XIII. LIMITATION

Present study has its own limitation like other study following are the limitation:

- The sample size was limited to 101 senior secondary students of age group 15-20years. Hence the possibility for wider generalization is limited.
- The researcher confined her study in one school of greater Noida, U.P.
- The non-probability was used to collect the sample.

XIV. RECOMMENDATION

- A study can be conducted to determine the preparedness of Final year Nursing Students for work as a professional Nurse.
- A qualitative study can be conducted to report early socialization and career choice in nursing among nursing students.
- A study can be conducted to assess the knowledge regarding girl abuse among school going girls of selected school of greater Noida.

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